

Determinants Of Pakistan-Afghanistan Relations Past, Present And Future

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: February 19,2021</p> <p>Accepted: April 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Relations, Terrorism, Cultural, Economic, Durand Line</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4721278</p>	<p><i>This article deals with the determinants of Pakistan relations with Afghanistan with reference to past present and future. There are numerous writings on the topic under consideration mainly in terrorism perspective but this study deals with the socio-cultural, political, economic and diplomatic relations between Pakistan and Afghanistan. Unique relationship of two Muslim and neighboring countries as peace and security of both countries is inter-linked. Although Pakistan and Afghanistan are facing many challenges but both of them are doing their best to handle the issues of terrorism, Pakhtunstan and Durand line. Present study will fill this gap. Since independence Pakistan has endeavored to maintain good relations with Afghanistan in pursuance of its policy to have good relations with Muslim Countries. By focusing on the need to improve socio-economic and cultural ties of both countries is very important for the peaceful co-existence of both the countries which will ensure peace and prosperity in the region. Pakistan, has its plus points and can be useful for the development of the Afghanistan while Afghanistan has colossal untapped mineral and labour assets which can help Pakistan to build its economy. Also, Afghans might have the ability to get coordinate access to Pakistan's ports of Arabian Sea, while Pakistanis can get steer access to Central Asian markets.</i></p>

Introduction

Since independence Pakistan has endeavored to maintain good relations with Afghanistan in pursuance of its policy to have good relations with Muslim Countries. Afghanistan is also one of the most important countries in Pakistan Foreign policy due to geographical location. Pakistan and Afghanistan share a border of 1200 Kilometers called Dur and line and across border people of both countries has close historical, ethnic and cultural ties. Unfortunately, the dynamics of Pakistan- Afghanistan relation and their mutual problems should not be viewed merely from the perspective of official policies and Kabul- Islamabad exchanges but interference of external powers prove important to enhance further relations. Consequently, under the influence of Super Powers "Great Game" Pak -Afghan relation can be studied.

What makes them important is not only its landmass but also the significant geo-strategic location Pakistan and Afghanistan enjoys. This peculiar location of Afghanistan and Pakistan has always attracted the major powers to exercise their influence in this rich region through the countries. Kingdom of Afghanistan has survived as an independent State with a loose confederacy of Afghan tribe, often troubled by internal strife and under pressure from outside powers. 1838-42.¹ British invaded Afghanistan and campaign proved disastrous and again in 1878 British occupied Qandahar and Kabul. With an assurance from British to support against Russian aggression, Amir Abdul Rehman Khan Signed the Durand line agreement establishing boundary that the successor State, Pakistan inherited in 1947. The issues of Durand line and Pakhtunistan formed the critical bases of Pakistan and Afghanistan relations. Afghanistan was the only country who raised objection on the membership of Pakistan in United Nation. President Daud Khan in 1976 tried to normalize relations, bringing Afghan leaders to the negotiating table for resolution of the disputes. In 1979 When Soviet Union invaded Afghanistan; major changes took place in Pakistan foreign policy towards Afghanistan. Pakistan government played a Vitol role in supporting the Afghan resistance movement and assisting Afghan refugees. This gave the Pakistan the status of front line supported by United States. As United States supplied Military equipment, strengthened its defense capabilities. Later on, Pakistan also supported Geneva accord resultantly Soviet troop's withdrawal from Afghanistan. In 1994 Taliban a new force emerged and Pakistan recognized Taliban's government and supported it. Post 9/11 scenario offered opportunities and challenges alike to Pakistan to reconsider its Afghanistan policy and renew its political and diplomatic ties with its Western neighbor. Since President Hamid Karzai became the Head of the Afghanistan, Pakistan and Afghanistan have relatively friendly terms with each other. Although some of the member s of Karzai's administration has criticized Pakistan, role in the US led was against terrorism and accused it interfering in Afghanistan's internal affairs however both of the Governments seemed determined to resolve their differences and cooperate with each other in war against

terrorism during the period under study. Afghanistan India relations and other countries like Iran and China's interest in Afghanistan have also great impact on Pakistan and Afghanistan relations. The continuing conflict engaged the United Nation and Afghanistan's neighbour in effort to bring about peace among the contending Afghan faction and help them reach political accommodation with each other.

Hypothesis:

In this perspective this study has tried to find out answers of the following questions, reasons, and motives behind Pakistan and Afghanistan relations.

- Did the contingencies of International politics push the two countries into each other arms?
- What are the impacts of war against terrorism on Pakistan and Afghanistan relations?
- What is the interest of India and other external powers in mutual relations of Pakistan and Afghanistan?
- Pakistan in spite of the weaker economic and technological capacity has played important role in regional affairs.

Objectives:

The basic objectives of this research are

- To rewrite history, set the record straight so as to remove the centuries old animosity between two Muslim countries, Afghanistan and Pakistan.
- To highlight the economic potential of both the countries, build better relations, realize the ideals of Pan Islam by forging economic ties, making the region a powerful block.
- To remove conflicts, barriers to peace to settle disputes and to end terrorism.
- To bring out cultural harmony existing between the people and making that the ground for cultivating stronger inter State relations.

Methodology:

Research will be conducted while using different techniques, documents, analysis, contents, and case studies. Library material was sufficient for the purpose of this research. Primary and secondary sources have been used. Approach will be historical, descriptive, analytical and comparative.

Pak-Afghan relations 1947-2001

Pakistan's initial years saw many fluctuations in the relations of Pakistan and Afghanistan. The two countries established initial ties in February 1948 and senior Pakistani Minister I I Chandigarh was sent to Kabul as ambassador. Afghan tribes tried to persuade the Afghan tribes but they were badly failed in their effort whereas this resulted decline in trade between two countries and Russian influence started to grow in this region. Khan Abdul Ghaffar Khan started a propaganda against Pakistan when he demanded third option in referendum if people wanted independent Pakhtoonistan. Afghanistan Government fully supported to him by giving this impression that NWFP wanted to join Afghanistan. In other words, Afghanistan opposed Pakistan to be Member of United States. When issue of Durand line was raised in Commonwealth as this boundary demarcation was done by Britain so Britain regarded as inrelationalborder between two countries and did not allow to violate it. Zahir Shah and Hussain Suhrawardypaid visit to Pakistan and Afghanistan during that time Pakistan Government allowed Afghanistan government to use Roads, Railways, Karachi seaport, for the export of Afghan goods. In 1960 Afghan Government started armed conflict in Bajour Agency and trade relations almost broke between two countries. Pashto speaking Population lived in Pakistan were two third and one third live in Afghanistan, they were in favor of Pakistan because life standard of Pakistani Pashtun was better than Kabul.

Pakistan at that point acted very wisely and continued to trade privileges to Afghanistan finally diplomatic relations were restored in 1963. It was Bhutto who redoubled his effort to smooth relations with Afghanistan. Pakistan allowed export of Afghan's fruit to India from Pakistan and fly Aeroplan from Pakistan to India. Although Zahir Shah and then Sardar Daud continued had hostile attitude but Pakistan continued its soft policy. Afghanistan was buffer State between Britain and Russia in last many years but Russia adopted different method of expansionism in 1977. When Noor M Tarakai became Prime Minister he wanted to introduce Socialism but Russia waned firm grip over this region. Russia entered its large-scale army in 1979 when Tarakai was assassinated which was of course was serious threat for the neighboring countries as well. Millions of Afghans migrated to Pakistan and Iran for safety and protection. Different resistance group emerged in Afghanistan as Islamic Alliance. They were fully supported by Pakistan. Pakistan not only provided asylum to the refugees but provided training and financial support to the Mujahidin which emerged sentiments of love and affections among the Afghani people. Soviet Union was very firm to get hold on Afghanistan but continuance resistance of Mujahidin and support of Pakistan made Moscow to change its expansion policy. Result Geneva accord was signed in 1988 In line with agreement Soviet had to leave Afghanistan on February 1964.ⁱⁱ In 1991 American changed their policy towards Afghanistan and orthodox Muslims were considered as their main armies/ Now communists and Mujahiden were active in Afghanistan. Kabul was engulfed in civil war. Taliban Milita was emerged in 1994 when Taliban Government was formed religious institutions were becoming strong day by day. Although both countries have begun to evolve friendly relations in regional frameworks, the fundamental issues remain intact. For

instance, Afghanistan still does not recognize Durand Line as international border between the two countries. Kabul blames Islamabad for fueling the insurgency in Afghanistan in order to destabilize the government of President Hamid Karzai and install a friendly or a more compliant government in Kabul. In turn, Islamabad alleges that Kabul has given shelter to Baloch nationalist insurgents and allows India to use Afghan territory to fuel the insurgency in Baluchistan.

Pakistan Afghanistan Relations after 9/11

Pakistan assumed exceptionally vital part after 9/11 particularly to destroy terrorism and to evacuate Taliban. It expanded uphold for revamping security, peace and new political request in Afghanistan that demonstrated convenient. Various political and security activities were taken by Pakistani government.ⁱⁱⁱ In spite of the fact that numerous delicate points as Durand line, Pashtuns and Taliban remained basic between Pakistan and Afghanistan throughout this time yet Pakistan remained extremely cautious to supervise all the scenarios. As president of Afghanistan Hamid Karzai who dependably remained condemning of Pakistan's part, every so often recognized the positive part of Pakistan in battling militancy in the district. In the gathering of Karzai and Ashfaq Kayani Through the counter- terrorism, Pakistan and Afghanistan consented to help brainpower imparting. Pakistani Government secured 1000 check post and presented Bio-Metric card for the penetration of outsiders and fringe security. Repatriation of the displaced people from Pakistan was the enormous issue for the Pakistani Government, with the assistance of UNHCR procedure of repatriation of evacuees to their villages was begun. Joint Jirga was religious circle; more than 1000 agent of both of the nation's partook. It was chosen that both of the nations might regard the regional respectability and non-impedance in one another affaires and they might try their hardest to end militancy and terrorism in the district. Afghanistan is a landlocked nation and dependably hinged on the participation of Iran, India and Pakistan to improve its worldwide exchange interfaces with the planet through oceans. Pakistan's financial relations with Afghanistan passed through different arranges after the formation of Pakistan. From 1947 to 1965 their budgetary relations saw ups and downs owing to political explanations yet once it closed Transit exchange Agreement of 1965, their financial ties set in spite of all chances. By closing the Transit exchange understanding of 2010 it ties between Pakistan and Afghanistan further combined since now they got universal exchange accomplice. Pakistan and Afghanistan might as well work together to kill pirating and to push travel exchange. As Jamaluddin Afghani and Allama Iqbal liked the thought of North-West British India and Afghanistan together structuring a solitary Muslim state. After 9/11 Despite of the political reservations and contradiction in both nations with respect to the Afghanistan Pakistan Transit Trade Treaty, both nations remained significant exchange accomplices. Joint Economic Commission played exceptionally essential and noteworthy chances to support up their financial relations between two nations particularly Pakistan assumed extremely significant part in reproduction of Afghanistan to advertise manageable and base improvement in the locale. Restoration of the Torkham-Jalabad Street by Pakistan to expedite exchange between two nations was secured. Enlargement of the chamman-Spinboldak rail connection was financed by Pakistan. \$330 billion was given by Pakistan in remaking and improvement of base in this time. Establishment of the joint Chamber of Commerce swayed private representatives to contribute one another nations. Transit Trade agreement 2010 is an alternate accomplishment of Both Countries. Pakistan stayed far ahead the extent that fare to Afghanistan is concerned, yearly figure touch \$4 billion dollar. Pakistan, as at present constituted is poor in minerals however rich in nourishment and filaments while Afghanistan has colossal untapped mineral and labour assets. Also, Afghans might have the ability to get coordinate access to Pakistan's ports of Arabian Sea, while Pakistanis can get steer access to Central Asian markets. A combination of the two might be monstrous conceivable outcomes not just for the individuals of the two nations yet for the whole Muslim planet.

External powers and Pakistan Afghanistan Relations

After 9/11 War on terror have come the investment of worldwide and local players in sharp canter. Being a prompt neighbors, the outer players' diversions in Afghanistan straight affect upon Pakistan's hobbies and security. These parts not just look at the investment of the outer players in the district however effects on Pakistan and Afghanistan relations. Further what confound the scenario is the contention around distinctive players especially Iran, India, and Pakistan as they seek after their own particular engages. Two major forces United States and Russia dependably go after impact and impart of the area's vigor and regular recourses. Indian association in Afghanistan likewise hurt investment of Pakistan and make issues between two nations. Bilateral relations of Pakistan and India with trilateral relations of Pakistan India and Afghanistan can bring them close and optional to sort out many problems like security issues, water and regional peace, and provide them access towards trade opportunities. Afghanistan can play very important role as link between Central Asia and South Asia. These three countries should build up confidence first and then should start cooperation in different factor like combating different extremist groups. Other local elements, NGOs should also play their part to establish good and long-term relations among these four countries. In this trilateral cooperation USA have to engage actively and constructively as US has to provide expertise and technical assistance.^{iv}

Pakistan Afghanistan and future prospects.

Pakistan should manage the relationship in a manner that was in Pakistan's national interest and learn from other countries, which maintained their ties with the US in ways that protected their national interest. Exemplifying China, although it had numerous potential points of conflict with the US: South China Sea, East China Sea, Japan, Taiwan etc., but still China's policy towards the US was that of productive engagement. Bilateral trade between the two nations exceeded half a trillion dollars and in 2003, China had 40,000 joint ventures with the Americans. Today, the largest number of students, over 100,000 annually, studying in American universities were Chinese nationals.^v China recognized that Europe and US were still the fountainhead of knowledge and technology, and was thus taking advantage of that. He concluded by stating that modernization entailed that policies were steered towards pursuing national interests, which had to be defined in the context of changing times. Tied to that is the need to streamline substantive, robust discussions on **trade and connectivity**.^{vi} Pakistan's vows to propel economic relations are creditworthy. Even during the raging pandemic, Pakistan decided to open 3 border crossings with Afghanistan, with a view to facilitating trade. Also, in the second review of APAPPS, both countries showed their willingness to negotiate terms of a new Afghanistan-Pakistan Transit Trade Agreement (APTTA). Recently, Pakistan also hosted a two-day seminar titled "Pakistan-Afghanistan Trade and Investment 2020" in a bid to explore new avenues for increasing bilateral trade. Pakistan should continue stressing the need for Afghanistan to take advantage from the mammoth China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). Not only will that help connect Pakistan's Khyber Pakhtunkhwa with Central Asian Republics (CARs), but will also give a veritable trading outlet to Afghanistan. China's eagerness to mitigate conflict in Afghanistan so as to promote economic connectivity and stability in its periphery, is a factor that could pull Afghanistan and Pakistan together on matters of trade and economics. **Perception management efforts must be initiated in a bid to reshape narratives and stereotypes, media from both sides must be engaged in a strategic manner.** Softer image-projections of Afghanistan and Pakistan through mainstream media will be instrumental in overcoming the ever-widening gulf of misperceptions. This should form the basis of a formal strategic communications scaffold, something that will go a long way in denying space for rigorous, dangerous disinformation operations that are carefully-planned to dent Pakistan's relations with its neighbors.

Conclusion

Relations between Pakistan and Afghanistan remained Unique in light of the fact that individuals of both nations have profound established passionate connection with one another. Ethnically and generally, they impart social amicability over the outskirts. Bury relational unions between tribes further improve solid ties between both of the nations. After 9/11 despite the fact that political issues at some point aggravate Diplomatic relations of both nations particularly Pakistan's stance for war against terrorism. Indian and Iranian association at some point exasperate investment connection however social ties between two nations remained dependably solid.^{vii} Whatever circumstances and tests were confronted by both of the nations, Pakistan upheld Afghanistan in each area. Pakistan dependably invited Afghan people to come in Pakistan and tried its hardest to expedite them in Pakistan as well as in their own nation too. In Education and health area Pakistan gave greatest help to Afghanistan. 144,909 Afghans were enlisted in Pakistani schools. Throughout this time Pakistan generated 26 Afghan PhD and 42 M.Phil'. Rahman Baba school cost \$4 Million was built and Allama Iqbal personnel of Arts at Kabul University take 10 Million was developed by Pakistan. Liaqat Ali Khan Engineering Faculty was built to expedite understudies

In Health division Pakistan financed Jinnah Hospital in Kabul and Kidney focuses in Jalalabad, drug was given to the doctor's facilities and numerous specialists and Para therapeutic staff were prepared in Pakistan. In training and health part as well as Pakistan backed Afghanistan in each field like in correspondence field, Pakistan gave workstations to IT understudies and Pakistan TV is working together with Afghan TV Arianna to create close interface between print and electorate media to advertise social trade. Pakistani Ambassador in Afghanistan Muhammad Sadiq remained extremely dynamic in this sense. People of Pakistan and Afghanistan despite the fact that remained dependably exceptional in relations.^{viii} Pakistan remained dependably in fever of to expedite Afghan siblings, after 9/11 occasion adapted all situation on worldwide level when US left no decision for Pakistan other than to be partner of US in War on terrorism. In fourth part it is talked over that war on fear has incredible effect on Pakistan and Afghanistan relations as this was the time period when dynamic obstruction was seen by key local players like Iran, India, Pakistan, and Russia with each one belittling their particular warlords. This came about into assisting the jumble that Afghanistan was experiencing. Each nation is dead set to administered its own particular impact on Afghanistan which influenced Pakistan and Afghanistan relations. Indian contribution in Afghanistan dependably irritates relations of both nations as Afghan have delicate corner for India since India is fifth giver in Afghanistan. American impact remained pivotal as both of the nations are subject to super powers. Russia and Iran dependably underpin Anti-Taliban, Northern Alliance in Afghanistan while Pakistan dependably upholds Taliban. Both of the nations tried to equalize Pakistan's association in Afghanistan by supporting distinctive Afghan bunches. As Musa Khan specified in his book that Russian Militant office give help to the Militants, who worked terrorist exercises in Pakistan. Pakistan and Afghanistan impart the past, present and future. It is paramount for the U.S. to comprehend that regardless of

what number of outer calculates, puts energetically to realize a sheltered passage out of Afghanistan, Pakistan's part remains essential. United States vicinity in Afghanistan is chance for Pakistan as issue of outskirts might be determined. China is in fever of Pakistan and Afghanistan sound relationship. On the grounds that stable Pakistan and Afghanistan is in fever of China. Last however not minimum is the part of India, created strategic connection with Afghan government and contribute vigorously against Pakistan. India expects that any sort of compromise that carry the Taliban into the Afghan government might empower Pakistan sponsored. India upheld Political compromise in Afghanistan. As Pakistan, as far as concerns it, should productively captivate Afghanistan, whatsoever levels. This is the best way to hold, console and improve Pakistan's impact with respect to Afghanistan. Pakistan gave more consideration regarding the recreation and advancement exertion in Afghanistan. Since Pakistan's backing is crucial for the dependability of Afghanistan, keep tabs on the reconstructive undertakings might give it more terrific edge. Additionally, if Pakistan gives aid to Afghanistan it will adjust the Indian impact simultaneously. Pakistan's venture in Afghanistan is recognized to be too substantial, and excessively discriminating to be squandered. Pakistan has an extraordinary stake in the development of a stable, prosperous and cordial Afghanistan. Enduring unsteadiness in Afghanistan could put incredible strain on Pakistan's economy and social order, and convey suggestions for its national security. Afghanistan needs to depend on Pakistan for its enormous unexplored assets and for its investment needs that open up chances for both the nations to work together where Pakistan can furnish mastery in the budgetary area.

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